

Attendance System Based On RFID

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Abstract—A The present system manages manual entry of attendance, the hurdle attached taking the attendance manually each by respective staff members and maintaining a hard copy record, later entering it to the system is tedious and error prone affair. The proposed system will give RFID number to each student and each student attendance is scanned and is automatically entered in attendance register

Keywords—RFID tags, RFID reader, Arduino

I. INTRODUCTION

RFID is an automatic identification and data gathering system that transmits information from the reader to the tagged module using radio frequency waves. RFID makes use of tags to identify objects. Each tag has a unique tag-id. Passive tags and active tags are the two main categories of tags. Passive tags are more common and less expensive than active tags. Passive tags, on the other hand, have more memory and no battery. Tags and readers are two halves of a wireless system known as Radio Frequency Identification (RFID). A reader is an electrical device that emits radio waves and receives signals from RFID tags using one or more antennas.

RFID transmits and receives data using electromagnetic waves in the radio frequency band. RFID tags are utilised in a variety of sectors, from security access cards to product tags at retail establishments. For a very long time, the prohibitive cost of the tags and readers prevented widespread commercial use. The use of RFID has grown as hardware costs have decreased. RFID tags are mostly utilised in manufacturing, healthcare, asset, and equipment tracking, vehicle tracking, and inventory management.

The use of RFID in Student attendance system will help to remove the hardship of manually entering the attendance by just scanning each student RFID tag which directly enter the database

The main components of the system are RFID tags, RFID reader, Arduino Uno. In this paper, an automatic RFID-based system for attendance register was designed using Arduino IDE software. The RFID reader allows the detection of RFID tag of an individual, it captures the user identifier ID and that particular individual is given attendance based on that and entered directly to the database.

Fig.1. Working of RFID

II. EXISTING SYSTEM AND PROPOSED SYSTEM

The current existing system mostly use paper and pen mode, it's a manual work so higher chance of occurring error and maintaining a hard copy is even harder

In paper[3], they use QR code technology which wont allow multiple user to scan at same time and the user should be in line of sight to be scanned, and its only read-only

In paper[8], fingerprint system is used, which have a high deployment cost, high chance of biometric malfunction like issues with recognition of damaged fingerprints like wound or grease

In paper[9], barcode scanners require a line of sight to scan each code individually and its difficult to do multiple scans at once.

In paper[10], it may cause privacy problems and can be manipulated and errors occurs can implicate innocent people

III. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

A. RFID Reader

The RC522 module has a total of 8 pins. For each of the communication protocols supported by this module, each pin on this module serves a different purpose. The MF RC522 is a highly integrated transmission module for 13.56 MHz contactless communication. The ISO 14443A/MIFARE mode is supported by the RC522. The RC522 - RFID reader is distinguished by an excellent modulation and demodulation algorithm that enables trouble-free 13.56 MHz RF communication. To communicate with microcontrollers, the module employs SPI.

Fig. 2. RFID Reader

B. RFID tags

A radio frequency identification tag (RFID tag) communicates with a reader module using electronic data. The majority of RFID tags have at least two components. The integrated circuit (IC) performs specialised tasks like data storage, processing, modulation, and demodulation of radio-frequency signals. The antenna for transmitting and receiving signals is the second component.

RFID cards are distinguished by their obvious physical properties and are used for specific applications. Every RFID card contains an antenna that is connected to an RFID IC, allowing it to receive, store, and transmit data via radio waves. RFID cards typically lack an internal power source and instead rely on passive RFID technology. The RFID card is powered by the electromagnetic energy collected and transmitted by the RFID reader.

Fig. 3. RFID tag

C. ARDUINO UNO

The ATmega328P is the basis for the Arduino UNO microcontroller board. It has six analogue inputs, a ceramic resonator operating at 16 MHz, 14 digital I/O pins (six of which can be used as PWM outputs), a USB port, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It includes everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply plug in a USB cable, an AC-to-DC adapter, or a battery to get started.

It accepts voltages ranging from 7 to 20 volts, but it can also be powered by an external 9-volt battery or a USB cable. In

some ways, it is similar to the Arduino Nano and Leonardo. The Uno board is the first in a series of USB-based Arduino boards. It served as the foundation for future Arduino releases, along with version 1.0 of the Arduino IDE. The bootloader preprogrammed on the board's ATmega328 enables the upload of new code without the need for an external hardware programmer.

Fig. 4. Arduino Uno

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

An Arduino UNO, an RFID reader, RFID tags, and Jumper wires are all components of the suggested system. The Arduino Uno serves as the brain of the proposed system. The card reader device reads the information when the card is shown. Using Arduino Ide the code is processed into Arduino Uno board

Fig. 5. Circuit Diagram of RFID Attendance System

Arduino	RFID-RC522
SDA	10
SCK	13
MOSI	11
MISO	12
GND	GND
RST	9
3.3V	3.3V

Fig. 6. Circuit Connection between RFID and Arduino

When RFID tag is scanned to the RFID scanner the input is taken into excel sheet. We use PLX-DAQ interface to connect scanner device to excel to get the values. The name of the owner ,date , unique RFID ID,time in and out is recorded into excel sheet

ID	Date	Name	Number	Card ID	Time IN	Time OUT
1	18-10-2022	Jeril KJ	295	78012299	12:57:41 PM	
2	18-10-2022	Jenma	304	23327206163	12:57:50 PM	
3	18-10-2022	Jeril KJ	295	78012299		12:58:03 PM
4	18-10-2022	Jenma	304	23327206163		12:58:08 PM

Fig. 7. Result in excel sheet Format

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE SCOPE

The proposed solution, an RFID-based attendance system, helps in recording the attendance automatically instead of a pen and paper. As the student arrives, the card reader gadget reads the data from the card when they swipe in. The result will be stored in an excel sheet The value from excel sheet will directly will be entered into database The

suggested system will be implemented in a college management system or anywhere attendance is taken. The RFID reader examines the RFID tag that is attached to each student and the attendance is marked.

The proposed system consists of trending technologies and have various aspects that can be implemented in the future to enhance and improve the attendance system in every industry

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Radio-frequency_identification
- [2] https://njccs.journals.ekb.eg/article_244463_f575fc0fe6aca9e99ccc2d9e4dc3234a.pdf
- [3] <https://docs.arduino.cc/hardware/uno-rev3>
- [4] https://njccs.journals.ekb.eg/article_244463_f575fc0fe6aca9e99ccc2d9e4dc3234a.pdf
- [5] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340246898_RFID_Based_Attendance_System_using_IoT
- [6] https://www.academia.edu/35755816/RFID_Based_Attendance_Management_System
- [7] <https://www.ijser.org/researchpaper/rfid-based-students-attendance-management-system.pdf>
- [8] <https://www.ijser.org/researchpaper/FINGERPRINT-BASED-ATTENDANCE-MANAGEMENT-SYSTEM.pdf>
- [9] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/245025631_Bar_Code_Scanner_Based_Student_Attendance_System_SAS
- [10] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341876647_Face_Recognition_based_Attendance_Management_System